

CONTRIBUTION OF IMPLEMENTING K3 ASPECT TO STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES IN CLASS XI PMKR SUBJECTS TKR DEPARTMENT AT SMKN 2 PAYAKUMBUH

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Abstract

This research was a mechanism regarding the Contribution of Implementing Aspects (K3) to student learning outcomes in class XI PMKR Subjects, TKR Department at SMKN 2 Payakumbuh. The application of K3 aspects in vocational high schools has a very big influence on students' practice learning outcomes, to create maximum learning outcomes, there is an important connection with the application of K3 aspects. This research method was descriptive correlational research which aimed to find out whether there is a relationship between K3 aspects and students' practical learning outcomes. In addition, to explain the research trial, there is a relationship between the application of occupational safety and health (K3) aspects to students' vocational learning outcomes. In the trial, several points will be measured later, namely testing the validation of the trial questionnaire and testing the reliability of the questionnaire.

Keywords: K3 aspects, practical learning, learning outcomes

INTRODUCTION

The development of vocational education in Indonesia is currently taking place very rapidly. This is in line with the establishment of many companies and various workplaces as the main destination for vocational school graduates to find work. The rapid development of technology in companies demands more understanding for employees, including understanding in the field of work safety.

Therefore, knowledge and familiarization with K3 culture needs to be studied and practiced from an early age by prospective employees, which in this case are vocational school students. K3 is important economically, morally, legally, occupational safety, and health have become important issues (Yamin, 2020). In general, K3 functions to minimize work accidents that

occur due to negligence committed during the work process (Mayasari & Julianto, 2023).

Good K3 behavior habits can shape worker behavior to be more concerned about work safety (Dinatha, 2023). Occupational Safety and Health (K3) is a program created by workers or employers as an effort to anticipate the occurrence work-related accidents and work-related illnesses by knowing what they are has the potential to cause accidents and occupational diseases and actions anticipatory if accidents and work-related illnesses occur (Balqist et al., 2023).

Improved safety and health Work is the duty of everyone involved in a job (Kisno et al., 2023). The use of Sanitation Hygiene and K3 modules was developed to be effectively used to support lectures and greatly

Submitted	Accepted	Published
10-11-2023	01-12-2023	01-12-2023

contribute to the development of science knowledge in the field of culinary (Putri et al., 2023).

For practical learning in workshops, students are required to apply work safety guidelines (Zebua, 2020). Vocational school students are directly involved in occupational health and safety issues, both during and after direct learning in the workshop. Students need to get used to implementing work safety guidelines when conducting direct learning in the workshop. K3 learning in general has a lot of theory and practice in implementation (Pane, 2021).

Activities in the workshop carry the risk of accidents if carried out carelessly (Yunizar, 2022). Work accidents in the automotive sector are usually caused by careless work and not following work SOPs properly, careless use of personal protective equipment (PPE), and inappropriate precautions in the workplace (Sulistiyono, 2020).

Researchers have made initial observations at SMK Negeri 2 Payakumbuh when carrying out PPL activities in the Department of Automotive Engineering, in these observations several things were found, such as in terms of students' vocational learning outcomes for pure grades they were still in the lower middle category. Many students are still below the KKM, especially in practical grades as attached in the attachment.

What is meant by pure grades are vocational subject grades where these grades are not processed into UTS or UAS grades, and related to understanding K3, researchers found that there were still several students in one class who did not understand the implementation of K3 aspects when doing practicum.

When researchers carried out PPL at SMK N 2 Payakumbuh in the Automotive Engineering Department, there were still several students who had not used PPE (Personal Protective Equipment) when carrying out the practicum, so one of the students had a work accident which resulted in one of his body parts being injured.

Third, regarding the role of schools in terms of K3, researchers obtained results

from interviews with three automotive vocational teachers that schools were more focused on providing socialization and training about K3 to teachers, but in reality, teachers had not provided effective socialization to students about the implementation of K3 in schools.

The research objective was a control tool that can be used as a guide so that this research can run as desired. The aimed of this research to explain the research trial of the relationship between the application of occupational safety and health (K3) aspects to student vocational learning outcomes. In the trial, several points will be measured later, namely testing the validation of the trial questionnaire and testing the reliability of the questionnaire.

Occupational Health and Safety

Labor has a big impact on the quality of a company or industry in managing and organizing its operations so that they run efficiently to achieve the set goals. However, it is important to remember that the potential risk of work accidents is also inherent in the workforce. Therefore, preventive measures must always be implemented by companies or industries to reduce the potential risk of work accidents.

Work safety reflects conditions in the work environment that are free from the risk of suffering, damage, or loss. Signs of work safety can be seen from efforts to maintain the welfare and safety of employees from possible suffering, loss, and damage, both physical and material. Based on this concept, it can be concluded that employees are considered to be working in a safe condition when they do not experience suffering, loss, or damage in any aspect.

Occupational Safety and Health in Vocational High Schools

Occupational Safety and Health, which is mostly implemented in Vocational High Schools (SMK), will have greater value with the release of government policy in developing education regarding the number of SMA and SMK. The Ministry of Education and Culture stated that it would increase the percentage of State Vocational

High Schools (SMK) from the previous 33 percent to 60 percent in 2020.

In addition, State Vocational Schools will receive an assignment Special Allocation Fund (DAK) budget in 2017. The aim of this assignment DAK fund is to increase the quality of Vocational High Schools (SMK).

One of the problems that often occurs in the workplace is accidents which cause things we don't want, such as material loss, injury, physical disability, and even death. How to prevent work accidents to avoid factors that have the potential to cause work accidents.

Preventive measures can be implemented by showing great vigilance when carrying out tasks and being characterized by a strong sense of responsibility. The use of body protective equipment also needs to become a habit and be in line with the type of work going.

Light Vehicle Maintenance Subject

Light vehicle engine maintenance is one of the subjects that students who take the light vehicle automotive engineering skills program must take. In learning about light vehicle engine maintenance, students are looking for knowledge related to how to carry out light vehicle engine maintenance.

The success of learning to maintain light vehicle engines can be seen from students' learning outcomes which can be measured by taking exams for basic theoretical competencies and practical tests for basic practical competencies.

Learning outcomes are understanding, knowledge, behavior, attitudes, competencies, and others obtained by students after carrying out the learning process. Competency is a quality that can be seen in a person, which involves an understanding of the knowledge, skills, and work ethic used to complete tasks or work following predetermined performance standards.

Learning outcomes are changes in behavior that emerge after participating in educational and learning interactions following educational targets. Evaluation of learning outcomes is carried out to measure achievement in education so that learning

outcomes should be in line with educational goals. Changes in behavior that originate from learning outcomes are caused by changes in the knowledge, skills, and abilities possessed by students after undergoing the learning process. Learning outcomes are knowledge, skills, and abilities that have been formed in students as a result of the learning process.

METHOD

This type of research was descriptive correlational research. Correlation research is research that aims to find out whether there is a relationship, if there is one, how close the relationship is, and whether the relationship is meaningful or not. It can be concluded that the correlational method aims to see the relationship and its strength, as well as to make estimates based on whether the relationship is strong or weak. The stronger the relationship, the higher the contribution.

The population was the entire research subject, the population in this research was class XI students of the Light Vehicle Engineering Skills Program. The population distribution in this research can be seen in the table below.

Table 1. Research Population

TKR Students	Number of Students
XI TKR A	30
XI TKR B	30
Total	60

The sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique that does not give each element or member of the population the same opportunity to be selected as a sample. The author chose the non-probability sampling technique to select the sample for this research, with a trial sample of 30 respondents from class XI TKR A and a research sample was 30 respondents from class XI TKR B.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research trials were carried out to get an initial picture of the data that will be collected later before conducting research

and are an absolute requirement for carrying out further action in research.

The instrument used in this research was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was used to obtain data on aspects of occupational safety and health (K3) on vocational learning outcomes. A questionnaire was a group of questions given in writing to 30 respondents. Respondents choose one alternative answer to each question.

The instruments in this research were prepared and developed based on the variables to be measured in XI TKR students in the form of indicators. The steps in compiling this questionnaire are as follows: analyzing variables into indicators, creating a questionnaire grid, developing questionnaire questions based on predetermined indicators, consulting the questionnaire with the supervisor, piloting research questionnaires, analyzing the trial results questionnaire (validity and reliability).

Instrument testing was carried out to find out whether the instrument used was truly valid and reliable. Instrument validity was the ability of a measuring instrument to be able to measure what must be measured according to its standards, while reliability was the ability of a measuring instrument to provide consistent measurement results at different times, as well as to determine the respondent's understanding of the question items.

Validity is a condition that describes the degree to which the instrument in question is capable of measuring what is to be measured. A measure that shows the level of validity or authenticity of an instrument. To determine the validity of the statement questionnaire items, Pearson's product-moment correlation formula is used which is explained as follows. An instrument is said to be reliable if it can measure accurately and consistently over time.

CONCLUSION

This research is an initial overview of a series of further research that will be carried out, from the results of researchers' observations regarding the implementation of K3 aspects in the Automotive Department of

SMKN 2 Payakumbuh and relating it to vocational subjects. The next stage of this research starts with creating a trial questionnaire with the theme of applying K3 aspects to student learning outcomes. The trial questionnaire that has been created will later go through the validation and reliability test stages. After carrying out this test, the results obtained will become initial guidelines or benchmarks for preparing research questionnaires, so that researchers can later continue the research to the next stage.

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